

Supplementary Information

This document presents supplementary figures showing the trend in daily maximum temperature.

Projection task

Figure S1: Change in annual mean daily maximum temperature between 1980-2019 and 2060-2099 for the projection assessment task. Results are shown for the ACCESS-ESM1-5 GCM (panel a), the BARPA-R RCM forced by that GCM (panel b), and for various bias correction methods applied to those RCM data (panels c-g).

Figure S2: Change in annual mean daily maximum temperature between 1980-2019 and 2060-2099 for the projection assessment task. Results are shown for the ACCESS-ESM1-5 GCM (panel a), the CCAM-v2203-SN RCM forced by that GCM (panel b), and for various bias correction methods applied to those RCM data (panels c-g).

Figure S3: Change in annual mean daily maximum temperature between 1980-2019 and 2060-2099 for the projection assessment task. Results are shown for the ACCESS-ESM1-5 GCM (panel a), the CCAM-v2105 RCM forced by that GCM (panel b), and for various bias correction methods applied to those RCM data (panels c-g).

Figure S4: Change in annual mean daily maximum temperature between 1980-2019 and 2060-2099 for the projection assessment task. Results are shown for the EC-Earth3 GCM (panel a), the BARPA-R RCM forced by that GCM (panel b), and for various bias correction methods applied to those RCM data (panels c-g).

Figure S5: Change in annual mean daily maximum temperature between 1980-2019 and 2060-2099 for the projection assessment task. Results are shown for the EC-Earth3 GCM (panel a), the CCAM-v2203-SN RCM forced by that GCM (panel b), and for various bias correction methods applied to those RCM data (panels c-g).

Figure S6: Change in annual mean daily maximum temperature between 1980-2019 and 2060-2099 for the projection assessment task. Results are shown for the BARPA-R RCM forced by the CESM2 GCM (panel a) and for various bias correction methods applied to those RCM data (panels b-f). Unlike the other GCMs, no raw CESM2 data were available.

Figure S7: Change in annual mean daily maximum temperature between 1980-2019 and 2060-2099 for the projection assessment task. Results are shown for the CCAM-v2203-SN RCM forced by the CESM2 GCM (panel a) and for various bias correction methods applied to those RCM data (panels b-f). Unlike the other GCMs, no raw CESM2 data were available.